

Toxicity Evaluation of Aqueous Extract of *Hybanthus enneaspermus* Leaves in Fluoxetine-induced Sexually-impaired Female Rats

¹Dikwa, M. A., ²Falana, M. B., ³Asinmi, M. R., ⁴Akanji, M. A. and ^{*3}Nurudeen, Q. O.

¹ Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, Federal University, Dutse, Nigeria.

² Department of Biological Sciences (Microbiology Unit), Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin.

³ Department of Biological Sciences (Biochemistry Unit), Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria.

⁴ Department of Biochemistry, Kwara State University, Malete, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Hybanthus enneaspermus, a traditional aphrodisiac was investigated for its potential to reverse anti-depressant-induced toxicity. This study explores the effects of an aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves (AEHEL) in fluoxetine-induced toxicity in female Wistar rats. Sixty, female rats (144.73 ± 5.96 g) were divided into six groups; control group (A), and five induced groups (B-F) and treated with distilled water (negative control), reference drug (Tadalafil at 20 mg/kg) and extract groups (250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg) respectively, once daily for seven days. The level of selected liver function indices significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased following the administration of fluoxetine and were significantly reversed following the administration of extract in a dose-dependent manner. Also, levels of selected kidney function indices and enzyme activities significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased and were significantly reversed following the administration of extract in a dose-dependent manner. There were no treatment-related histo-architectural changes in the organs of the animals. Overall, the conducted toxicity evaluation of AEHEL in Wistar rats revealed no deleterious effects, henceforth, suggesting that it could be safe for users using it as an oral remedy for sexual inadequacies in females.

Keywords: Functional toxicity; Herbal medicine; *Hybanthus enneaspermus*; Lethality; Structural toxicity

INTRODUCTION

When using herbal remedies, safety and effectiveness are crucial factors to take into account. Although some herbs seem to be somewhat safer and healthier than pharmaceutical substances, however, since they contain potent, pharmacologically active components, it is important to utilize all medications, including herbal ones, with caution (Ardalan and Rafieian-Kopaei, 2013). Throughout history, traditional medical techniques such as acupuncture, herbal medicines, and indigenous traditional medicine have been utilized extensively. There is little scientific data to support the safety and effectiveness of the majority of herbal treatments, even though 25% of contemporary medications are derived from traditionally used herbs (Zhang, 2015). Much scientific research has been conducted on the potential of these herbs that have been used in medicine for millennia to cure a variety of ailments, produce new pharmaceuticals and confirm their effectiveness. The major importance that medicinal plant products play in healthcare is highlighted by the fact that their

annual global market value surpasses \$100 billion (Fayiah *et al.*, 2023).

Hybanthus enneaspermus, is a member of the Violaceae plant family and is used as a traditional medicinal herb. Numerous pharmacological characteristics have been documented, such as antidiabetic, antiplasmodial, antibacterial, anticonvulsant, nephroprotective, and aphrodisiac actions (Patel *et al.*, 2013). Traditionally, this perennial medicinal plant is used to treat infections, diabetes, malaria, and urinary tract issues (Rajsekhar, 2016). Additionally, cytotoxic cyclotides with possible anticancer effects have been found in *Hybanthus enneaspermus* in recent investigations (Du *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, it has also been reported to have the potential to reverse anti-depressant-induced sexual dysfunction in female rats (Dikwa *et al.*, 2023). The plant is a major area of interest for research because of its wide range of bioactivities.

One popular medication that frequently causes unwanted sexual side effects is fluoxetine. Decreased desire for sex, delayed or absent

*Corresponding author. E-mail: quadriolaide@yahoo.com

orgasm in women, and delayed ejaculation in males are some examples of these side effects (Chen, 2016). Studies have confirmed that decreased sexual desire and pleasure can result from fluoxetine-induced sexual dysfunction (Dikwa *et al.*, 2023, Nurudeen *et al.*, 2023). Many women seek herbal therapies for sexual dysfunction for several reasons, including cost, accessibility, and the belief that plants have few side effects. There is a dearth of experimental evidence in the public scientific literature to ascertain the plant's toxicological effects on female Wistar rats. Therefore, this study investigated the safety profile of the aqueous extract of *Hybanthus enneaspermus* leaves using sexually dysfunctional female Wistar rats as animal models.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and authentication of the plant materials

The leaves of *H. enneaspermus* were acquired at a local market in Ilorin West local government, Kwara State, Nigeria. To ensure accuracy, a botanist performed identification and authentication at the University of Ilorin Herbarium in Ilorin, Nigeria. A formal voucher sample was lodged under the UIH 001/1092 reference number.

Experimental Animals

Sixty sexually active, healthy, and inbred female Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) were acquired from the Department of Biochemistry Animal Holding Unit at the University of Ilorin, located in Ilorin, Nigeria. Their weight was 144.73 ± 5.96 g. The rats were kept in an Animal House at room temperature in hygienic, well-maintained cages. They had unrestricted access to tap water and were given rat pellets. Throughout the experiment, the guidelines provided by the National Institutes of Health (NIH Publication No. 80-23) and the European Convention for the Use of Laboratory Animals for Scientific Purposes (ETS-123) were strictly adhered to. To ensure the animals' well-being and appropriate treatment throughout the inquiry, the institution's regulations for animal care and usage were scrupulously followed as approved by the Al-Hikmah University Ethical Review Committee (HUI/UERC/2023/020).

Reagents and assay kits

The firms that manufacture fluoxetine and Tadalafil are Evans Therapeutic Limited in Isolo, Lagos state, Nigeria, and V.S. International Pvt. Limited in Dabhel, Daman, India respectively.

Sigma-Aldrich Inc., based in St. Louis, Missouri, USA, produces assay kits for serum electrolyte, bilirubin, albumin, creatinine, urea, total protein, alkaline phosphatase, alanine aminotransferase, and aspartate aminotransferase. The remaining reagents were analytical-grade goods that were kept in a clean, tight reagent bottle after being newly prepared in distilled water.

Preparation of plant extracts

The leaves were properly cleaned under running water and then allowed to dry for 72 hours at room temperature. After being dried and mashed in an electric blender, the leaves were stored in an airtight container. Over 48 hours at 27°C, 100 g of the powdered material was macerated in an aqueous solvent. The maceration method involved shaking often and filtering through cheesecloth. After the filtrate was allowed to evaporate in a rotating evaporator, a sticky residue was left behind. To get the required dosages of 250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg body weight, this residue was reconstituted in distilled water. The doses were determined using data from an ethnobotanical survey; the most often specified number was 500 mg/kg body weight. The doses of 1000 and 250 mg/kg body weight were selected as they represent twice and half the often-mentioned dose of 500 mg/kg body weight.

Animal grouping and administration of plant extracts

A total of sixty female rats acclimated for two weeks were split into six groups (A to F), each with 10 animals, in a randomized design. Out of these, fifty female rats were given an oral dosage of fluoxetine (15 mg/kg body weight, prepared daily in distilled water) for 14 days to induce sexual dysfunction. The grouping is as follows;

Group A: Rats that received 0.5ml of distilled water

Group B: Rats induced into sexual dysfunction and administered 0.5ml of distilled water

Group C: Rats induced into sexual dysfunction and administered 0.5ml of 20 mg/kg body weight of Tadalafil

Group D: Rats induced into sexual dysfunction and administered 0.5ml of 250 mg/kg body weight of the extract

Group E: Rats induced into sexual dysfunction and administered 0.5ml of 500 mg/kg body weight of the extract

Group F: Rats induced into sexual dysfunction and administered 0.5ml of 1000 mg/kg body weight of the extract

The different animal groups were treated as described above once daily using a plastic oropharyngeal cannula for seven days.

Tissue and serum supernatant preparation

The protocol used by Nurudeen and Yakubu (2016) for the preparation of the tissue and serum supernatants. The rats were anesthetized on day 8, with fumes of diethyl ether to induce unconsciousness, and had their jugular veins cut. Blood samples were collected, allowed to coagulate for 15 minutes, and then placed into dry, clean centrifuge tubes. The tubes were centrifuged for 10 minutes at $894 \times g$. After the resulting sera were aspirated using a Pasteur's pipette, they were refrigerated awaiting additional biochemical analysis. The liver and kidney were then carefully removed from the animals by rapid dissection, blotting them, and storing them in an ice-cold solution containing 0.25M sucrose. The organs were separated and homogenized in an ice-cold 0.25M sucrose (1:5 w/v) solution. The organs were centrifuged for 10 minutes at $1789 \times g$, and the supernatants were then utilized to test several biochemical markers.

Determination of Biochemical parameters

The parameters of the biochemical origin were determined using the established protocols of the following: Bartels and Bohmer (1972) for creatinine; Doumas *et al.* (1971) for albumin; Gornall *et al.* (1949) for total protein; Jendrassik and Grof (1938) for total and conjugated bilirubin; and Veniamin and Verkirtzi (1970) for urea. To determine the concentrations of uric acid and serum electrolytes, the methods of Tietz (1995) were employed. Following the guidelines provided by Reitman and Frankel (1957), Beutler (1984), Wright *et al.* (1972a), Wright *et al.* (1972b), and Szasz (1969), the activities of alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphatase, and gamma-glutamyl transferase were determined respectively.

Data Analysis

Ten sets of duplicate data were used to calculate the mean and standard error of the mean, which allowed for the determination of statistical significance. A one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was also done. GraphPad Prism 9.01 (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego, California, United States) was used for statistical analysis. At the significance level of $p < 0.05$, the findings were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Selected Liver function indices of fluoxetine-induced sexual dysfunction female rats

Serum total protein, serum albumin, globulin, total bilirubin and direct bilirubin levels in sexually active female rats were significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased by fluoxetine treatment in contrast to the animals who were treated with distilled water. Furthermore, the levels of the liver function indices in the serum of the female rats treated with fluoxetine showed significant increases ($p < 0.05$) at all treatment doses when compared to the animals treated with distilled water. When the fluoxetine-induced sexual dysfunction group of female rats was given the reference medication (tadalafil), the concentrations of all liver function indices except globulin were not significantly different ($p > 0.05$) from the animals treated with distilled water (Table 1).

Selected kidney function indices of fluoxetine-induced sexual dysfunction female rats

Serum urea, uric acid, creatinine, sodium and chloride ion levels were significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated in sexually active female rats administered fluoxetine in contrast to the animals treated with distilled water (Table 2). The levels of the kidney function indices in the serum of the female rats treated with fluoxetine showed significant decreases ($p < 0.05$) at all treatment (250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg) doses when compared to the animals treated with distilled water. Nevertheless, neither the reference medication (tadalafil) nor the extract's administration at any of the studied dosages substantially ($p < 0.05$) changed the levels of potassium and phosphate ions in the rat serum in contrast to the animals administered with distilled water (Table 2).

Table 1: Selected Liver function indices of sexual dysfunction in female rats administered aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves

Treatment	Serum total protein (mg/dl)	Albumin (mg/dl)	Globulin (mg/dl)	Total bilirubin (mg/dl)	Direct bilirubin (mg/dl)
Distilled water	93.38 ± 5.13 ^a	42.64 ± 4.82 ^a	37.90 ± 4.75 ^a	2.33 ± 0.27 ^a	0.54 ± 0.06 ^a
Fluoxetine + distilled water	69.58 ± 4.11 ^b	31.31 ± 3.47 ^b	30.72 ± 2.63 ^b	2.01 ± 0.29 ^b	0.43 ± 0.09 ^b
Fluoxetine + 20 mg/kg tadalafil	90.71 ± 5.63 ^a	39.64 ± 3.91 ^a	30.98 ± 4.38 ^b	2.35 ± 0.33 ^a	0.50 ± 0.08 ^a
Fluoxetine + 250 mg/kg extract	79.39 ± 4.39 ^c	32.44 ± 4.26 ^b	30.61 ± 3.72 ^b	2.05 ± 0.41 ^b	0.45 ± 0.05 ^b
Fluoxetine + 500 mg/kg extract	85.64 ± 6.31 ^d	36.97 ± 4.54 ^c	34.75 ± 2.16 ^c	2.11 ± 0.28 ^c	0.47 ± 0.02 ^c
Fluoxetine + 1000 mg/kg extract	89.53 ± 4.67 ^a	40.47 ± 3.09 ^a	36.12 ± 3.84 ^a	2.26 ± 0.27 ^a	0.55 ± 0.04 ^a

Data are the means of ten replicates ± SEM. Test values with superscripts different from the control across the group for each parameter are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2: Selected Kidney function indices of sexual dysfunction in female rats administered aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves

Treatment	Urea (mg/dl)	Uric (mg/dl)	Acid	Creatinine (mg/dl)	Serum electrolytes (mmol/L)			
					Na ⁺	K ⁺	Cl ⁻	PO ₃ ²⁻
Distilled water	19.82 ± 2.76 ^a	7.43 ± 1.05 ^a	1.97 ± 0.31 ^a	121.18 ± 10.23 ^a	4.51 ± 0.14 ^a	95.09 ± 12.27 ^a	1.53 ± 0.15 ^a	
Fluoxetine + distilled water	30.16 ± 4.92 ^b	20.15 ± 1.37 ^b	5.42 ± 0.16 ^b	159.26 ± 16.98 ^b	4.92 ± 0.34 ^a	137.46 ± 9.03 ^b	1.58 ± 0.15 ^a	
Fluoxetine + 20 mg/kg tadalafil	20.29 ± 2.04 ^a	14.42 ± 1.19 ^a	2.27 ± 0.15 ^a	125.07 ± 14.56 ^a	4.68 ± 0.24 ^a	97.75 ± 13.48 ^a	1.20 ± 0.22 ^a	

Fluoxetine + 250 mg/kg extract	29.92 ± .21 ^b	18.88 ± 1.85 ^b	4.91 ± 0.12 ^b	140.14 ± 12.25 ^c	5.14 ± 0.17 ^a	123.12 ± 10.13 ^c	1.43 ± 0.15 ^a
Fluoxetine + 500 mg/kg extract	21.68 ± 2.07 ^a	13.75 ± 1.22 ^c	3.54 ± 0.43 ^c	136.48 ± 10.07 ^c	4.03 ± 0.18 ^a	117.89 ± 11.94 ^c	1.42 ± 0.26 ^a
Fluoxetine + 1000 mg/kg extract	18.09 ± 3.26 ^a	9.39 ± 1.08 ^a	2.15 ± 0.36 ^a	120.29 ± 13.33 ^a	5.44 ± 0.16 ^a	102.27 ± 13.22 ^a	1.45 ± 0.18 ^a

Data are the means of ten replicates ± SEM. Test values with superscripts different from the control across the group for each parameter are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Table 3: The tissues and serum alkaline phosphatase activities of sexual dysfunction female rats administered aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves

Treatment	Liver Alkaline phosphatase (U/L/mg protein)	Kidney Alkaline phosphatase (U/L/mg protein)	Serum Alkaline phosphatase (U/L/mg protein)
Distilled water	22.34 ± 2.92 ^a	37.53 ± 4.05 ^a	1.96 ± 0.34 ^a
Fluoxetine + distilled water	39.56 ± 2.21 ^b	42.29 ± 4.15 ^b	3.41 ± 0.26 ^b
Fluoxetine + 20 mg/kg tadalafil	25.87 ± 3.69 ^a	37.77 ± 2.08 ^a	1.87 ± 0.22 ^a
Fluoxetine + 250 mg/kg extract	35.18 ± 2.31 ^c	36.29 ± 3.47 ^a	2.68 ± 0.29 ^a
Fluoxetine + 500 mg/kg extract	30.49 ± 3.08 ^d	37.01 ± 3.23 ^a	2.22 ± 0.29 ^a
Fluoxetine + 1000 mg/kg extract	23.15 ± 3.27 ^a	39.42 ± 4.07 ^a	1.93 ± 0.28 ^a

Data are the means of ten replicates ± SEM. Test values with superscripts different from the control across the group for each parameter are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Selected enzyme activity of fluoxetine-induced sexual dysfunction female rats

Compared to the female rats that were given distilled water only, the rats' serum, liver, and kidney showed a substantial ($p<0.05$) increase in alkaline phosphatase activity after receiving fluoxetine (Table 3). The extract at all studied dosages (250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg) substantially ($p<0.05$) reduced the activity of alkaline phosphatase in the animals' liver, kidney, and serum significantly reversing the fluoxetine effect. The reference medication, tadalafil, was given to rats with fluoxetine-induced sexual dysfunction, and this pattern of decline in the enzyme's activity was comparable to the distilled water group (Table 3).

When fluoxetine was given to female rats that were sexually active, the activity of acid phosphatase in their liver and kidney was significantly ($p<0.05$) increased compared to that of female rats who were given distilled water alone (Table 4). The extract at all studied dosages (250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg) substantially ($p<0.05$) reduced the activity of acid phosphatase in the animals' liver and kidney significantly reversing the fluoxetine effect. Nevertheless, neither the reference medication (tadalafil) nor the extract's administration at any of the studied dosages substantially ($p<0.05$) changed the levels of serum acid phosphatase in contrast to the animals administered with distilled water (Table 4).

The activity of aspartate transaminase as well as alanine transaminase in the liver and serum were

significantly ($p<0.05$) increased with the administration of fluoxetine (Table 5). The administration of the extract at all studied dosages and the reference medication (tadalafil) significantly ($p<0.05$) reversed the level of aspartate transaminase and alanine transaminase activity in the rat liver and serum (Table 5).

When sexually active female rats were given fluoxetine, the level of liver and serum gamma-glutamyl transferase activity significantly ($p<0.05$) decreased in comparison with the animals treated with distilled water. The administration of the extract at all the investigated dosages and the reference medication (tadalafil) significantly ($p<0.05$) reversed the level of liver and serum gamma-glutamyl transferase activity in the rat liver and serum (Table 6).

Histological examination of the liver and kidney of sexual dysfunction female rats

All treated animals' kidneys retained their medullary and cortical architecture, showing no signs of tubular degeneration, necrosis, fatty alterations, interstitial inflammation, or distortion on the proximal and distal convoluted tubules (Plates 1). Furthermore, all five experimental animals showed no signs of adhesion, inflammation, or necrosis. The lobular architecture, hepatocytes, central vein, and portal tracts of the liver of the animals treated with the extract were all within normal physiology (Plates 2).

Table 4: The tissues and serum acid phosphatase activities of sexual dysfunction female rats administered aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves

Treatment	Liver Acid Phosphatase (U/L/mg protein)	Kidney Acid phosphatase (U/L/mg protein)	Serum Acid phosphatase (U/L/mg protein)
Distilled water	13.62 ± 1.78 ^a	17.48 ± 2.05 ^a	0.74 ± 0.14 ^a
Fluoxetine + distilled water	31.15 ± 2.01 ^b	34.34 ± 3.97 ^b	0.71 ± 0.25 ^a
Fluoxetine + 20 mg/kg tadalafil	15.94 ± 2.83 ^a	20.84 ± 2.16 ^a	0.79 ± 0.19 ^a
Fluoxetine + 250 mg/kg extract	26.25 ± 2.32 ^c	30.27 ± 2.14 ^c	0.61 ± 0.25 ^a
Fluoxetine + 500 mg/kg extract	21.53 ± 2.07 ^d	30.09 ± 3.21 ^c	0.71 ± 0.25 ^a
Fluoxetine + 1000 mg/kg extract	16.18 ± 1.26 ^a	25.45 ± 2.06 ^d	0.76 ± 0.18 ^a

Data are the means of ten replicates ± SEM. Test values with superscripts different from the control across the group for each parameter are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Table 5: Liver and serum alanine transaminase and aspartate transaminase activities of sexual dysfunction female rats administered aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves

Treatment	Liver ALT (U/L/mg protein)	Serum ALT (U/L/mg protein)	Liver AST	Serum AST (U/L/mg protein)
Distilled water	48.56 ± 5.08 ^a	33.52 ± 3.07 ^a	25.05 ± 2.22 ^a	17.87 ± 2.07 ^a
Fluoxetine + distilled water	62.12 ± 6.28 ^b	57.24 ± 3.29 ^b	29.43 ± 1.06 ^b	32.35 ± 1.27 ^b
Fluoxetine + 20 mg/kg tadalafil	51.47 ± 3.01 ^a	33.49 ± 4.05 ^a	24.98 ± 3.28 ^a	16.55 ± 2.08 ^a
Fluoxetine + 250 mg/kg extract	58.62 ± 4.92 ^c	50.89 ± 3.62 ^c	25.41 ± 3.04 ^a	29.28 ± 1.31 ^c
Fluoxetine + 500 mg/kg extract	57.78 ± 4.13 ^c	42.15 ± 2.19 ^d	25.92 ± 2.85 ^a	29.15 ± 2.27 ^c
Fluoxetine + 1000 mg/kg extract	50.29 ± 3.33 ^a	35.73 ± 3.94 ^a	23.24 ± 2.06 ^a	20.94 ± 1.87 ^d

Data are the means of ten replicates ± SEM. Test values with superscripts different from the control across the group for each parameter are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Table 6: Liver and serum gamma-glutamyl transferase activities of sexual dysfunction female rats administered aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves

Treatment	Liver gamma-glutamyl transferase (U/L/mg protein)	Serum gamma-glutamyl transferase(U/L/mg protein)
Distilled water	21.56 ± 2.08 ^a	9.52 ± 2.07 ^a
Fluoxetine + distilled water	34.12 ± 3.28 ^b	17.24 ± 1.29 ^b
Fluoxetine + 20 mg/kg tadalafil	20.47 ± 4.01 ^a	11.49 ± 3.05 ^a
Fluoxetine + 250 mg/kg extract	30.62 ± 2.92 ^c	16.89 ± 1.62 ^b
Fluoxetine + 500 mg/kg extract	26.78 ± 2.13 ^d	16.15 ± 2.19 ^b
Fluoxetine + 1000 mg/kg extract	22.29 ± 2.33 ^a	10.73 ± 2.94 ^a

Data are the means of ten replicates ± SEM. Test values with superscripts different from the control across the group for each parameter are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Plate 1: Histopathological examination of the kidney by hematoxylin-eosin staining reveals normal cytostructure (magnification $\times 400$ & 100).

Plate 2: Histopathological examination of the liver by hematoxylin-eosin staining reveals normal cytostructure (magnification $\times 400$ & 100).

DISCUSSION

Medicinal plants are a rich source of a diverse range of secondary metabolites, and a noticeable number of regularly prescribed conventional medications originate from herbs. The severe problem phytomedicines face, despite of their widespread use, is the dearth of scientific data supporting their mechanism of action and *in vivo* safety profile. This necessitates the conduct of meticulously planned toxicity studies based on stipulated guidelines to claim the safety of medicinal plants used in various traditional practices. Negative effects from herbal medications can range in severity from minimal to severe (Posadzki *et al.*, 2013).

Liver function tests (LFTs) are blood tests that are used to assess liver function, monitor liver illness or damage, and assist in the diagnosis of liver disorders. These tests gauge blood levels of certain proteins and enzymes that may point to liver issues (Gowda *et al.*, 2009). Total protein tests measure the amount of protein in the blood, and abnormal levels can indicate various health conditions, including liver disease and kidney disease. Albumin is one of several proteins synthesized in the liver and is a major component of plasma. The significant decrease in the level of serum albumin and total protein following the administration of fluoxetine may mean liver damage or disease.

Decreased production of albumin can also result from severe chronic hepatic impairment, which is a feature of chronic and advanced hepatic cirrhosis. The liver's synthetic functions appear to be significantly reversed by *H. enneaspermus* in a dose-dependent manner, thereby restoring the functionality of the liver. This demonstrates the hepatoprotective properties of *H. enneaspermus* providing protection against liver damage and promoting liver health. This result is in line with studies that have demonstrated the hepatoprotective properties of *H. enneaspermus* against paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity in mice (Arman *et al.*, 2022).

The levels of total and direct bilirubin are significant markers of liver health and possible damage. As red blood cells break down, bilirubin is produced as a byproduct and is recognized to have certain harmful properties. High bilirubin levels, especially in the unconjugated form, can cause toxicity, especially in the central nervous system, where it can cause bilirubin encephalopathy, also known as kernicterus. The significant increase in the total bilirubin shows that the bile duct obstruction might have caused total or direct bilirubin to build up and then be released into the circulation.

Kidney function indices

Toxins and waste products must be removed from the blood by the kidneys, and poor kidney function can cause dangerous compounds to build up in the body. Kidney function markers are crucial for evaluating the potential toxicity of drugs and plant extracts. Serum electrolytes (sodium, potassium, chloride, and phosphate) and serum urea, uric acid, and creatinine are among them. These markers also reveal information about the nephron's capacity to function at the glomerular and tubular levels (Yakubu *et al.*, 2009). The kidney's first filtering site, the glomerulus, filters blood into a filtrate that is then processed further in the renal tubules. Renal function depends on both the rate of filtration and the reabsorption of essential nutrients.

Since the fundamental function of the kidneys is to filter waste materials and excess fluids from the blood, renal injury can result from either a high glomerular filtration rate (GFR) or a lack of glomerular filtration. An impaired glomerular filtration rate (GFR) can lead to waste products and toxins building up in the body, which can cause several health problems. Muscle tissue breaks down as muscles burn up energy, releasing the toxin creatinine into the blood, which the kidneys filter out of the circulation and eliminate through urine. After fluoxetine was administered, there was a significant decrease in creatinine levels, which might indicate renal weakness or injury. Creatinine remains in the blood and progressively accumulates in renal diseases.

The kidney also regulates the excretion of uric acid and urea. The significant increase in urea and uric acid levels after fluoxetine treatment may indicate kidney disease or dehydration. High amounts of uric acid (hyperuricemia) caused by the body producing a high amount of uric acid, decreased excretion, or a combination of both can also lead to the accumulation of crystals in joints, which could result in kidney stones and perhaps harm to the kidneys. Elevated levels of sodium (Na^+) and chloride (Cl^-) after fluoxetine treatment may suggest tubular damage since these electrolytes are reabsorbed in the distal tubules. However, the extract has a selective effect on potassium (K^+) and phosphate (PO_3^{2-}) ions in the serum of animals treated with distilled water, fluoxetine and tadalafil, while the extract has no significant impact on it. This study demonstrates that the fluoxetine-induced alterations in these biomolecule levels were dramatically restored by the extract administration. This would suggest that the

extract could be able to reverse the changes in biomolecule levels that fluoxetine causes in animals, therefore normalizing the biological processes that have been disrupted.

Enzyme Activities

The presence of certain enzymes in the serum that do not originate in the extracellular fluid can be indicative of tissue injury or damage. This is because, under normal circumstances, these enzymes are contained within the cells and their presence in the serum may signal a disruption of cell membrane integrity, allowing the enzymes to leak into the bloodstream (Arun *et al.*, 2012). Long before structural damage is visible using standard histology methods, enzymes can reveal cellular damage brought on by chemical substances. This is because enzymes are sensitive indicators of cellular integrity and function, and their release into the extracellular space can signal damage to various cellular components (Vona *et al.*, 2021). Two of the widely distributed enzymes found in the plasma membrane that may be utilized to gauge the membrane's integrity are alkaline phosphatase (ALP) (Akanji *et al.*, 1993) and acid phosphatase (ACP), they are regarded as a "marker" enzyme of the lysosomal membrane according to Collins and Lewis (1971).

After treatment with the fluoxetine, there was a significant increase in the activities of kidney, liver, and serum ALP, as well as the kidney and liver ACP, but there was no increase in the activities of ACP in the serum. The observed increase might perhaps be attributed to the stress placed on the liver and kidney due to their respective roles in the metabolism and excretion of fluoxetine. The tissues may have accelerated the production of the enzymes from scratch in an effort to counteract the stress caused by the fluoxetine exposure. In certain tissues, increased activity of certain enzymes has been seen under varying stress situations. Treatment with the Tadalafil and the extract reversed significantly, the activities of kidney, liver and serum ALP, as well as kidney ACP.

The reversal by the extract is also dose-dependent. According to Shahjahan *et al.* (2004), the aminotransferases, such as aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT), are useful indicators of liver cytolysis and may be used to measure liver damage. An effective metric for monitoring and evaluating liver health is ALT and AST, an enzyme that is mostly found in the liver and whose blood levels can rise in response to liver injury. When liver cells are injured, both enzymes are sent into circulation, and a straightforward blood test can determine the amounts of each enzyme. The hepatic

and serum ALT and AST activity significantly increased with fluoxetine administration. Damage to the muscles or liver may have contributed to the increase in serum enzyme activity. Liver cytolysis is linked to an increase in aminotransferases like AST and ALT, which is indicative of liver injury. The pancreas, intestinal tract, hepatocytes, and renal tubules are among the tissues that contain the microsomal enzyme gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT). By moving peptides across the cell membrane, GGT contributes significantly to glutathione metabolism and maintains glutathione homeostasis (Gowda *et al.*, 2009). When fluoxetine was administered, there was a significant increase in both the serum and hepatic GGT activity. Certain liver diseases, including chronic hepatitis C infection, have been linked to elevated GGT levels. When there is a bile duct obstruction or other bile duct problems, the levels of GGT, the most sensitive liver enzyme test for identifying bile duct problems, might increase. Following the administration of the aqueous extract of *H. Enneaspermus* leaves, the research observed a dramatic reversal in GGT activity in both the serum and the liver. This could occur from the underlying liver or bile duct problems being resolved.

Histopathological studies

To evaluate possible morphological changes in tissues following exposure to chemical substances, including plant extracts, histological examinations are frequently carried out. The findings from histology investigations revealed that the kidney section showed renal tissue with preserved architecture comprising normal glomeruli, tubules and vessels and there are no features of acute or chronic damage. Liver sections showed liver tissue with largely preserved architecture composed of normal hepatocytes, portal tracts and central veins and there are no features of chronic damage.

The uterus sections showed normal myometrial (composed of fascicles of smooth muscle) and endometrial tissue (composed of preserved glandular epithelium) and there were no abnormalities seen. Ovary sections showed ovarian tissue composed of developing follicles and corpora lutea of varying sizes. The results generally show the absence of gross abnormalities or distortions in the histoarchitecture of the ovary, uterus, liver, and kidney of the animals suggesting that there was no treatment-related structural toxicity in this context. These results are consistent with a report by Monsees and Opuwari (2017), who reported no adverse changes in the ovary, uterus, kidney, and liver sections of all treated groups

of experimental rats given unfermented and fermented rooibos (*Aspalathus linearis*) at doses of 2% and 5%.

CONCLUSION

Toxicity evaluation of herbal medicines is necessary to provide safety assurance of their subsequent usage. The magnitude of toxicity of the medicinal plants is determined through lethality and degeneration of the vital organs particularly the liver and the kidney tissues or cells. *The in vivo* toxicity evaluation of the aqueous extract of *H. enneaspermus* leaves revealed no mortality cases even at the highest dose of 1000 mg/kg body weight of the female Wistar rats suggesting that the extract could be used as an oral remedy for sexual inadequacies in females. However, studies with higher doses and the actual mechanism of action of the extract on the liver and kidney of sexually impaired animals will have to await the outcome of further studies.

Author's contribution: QON and MAA conceptualized the work and drafted the manuscript. MAD, MRA, and MBF carried out the experiment and data analysis. All authors participated in the preparation as well as the revision of the manuscript. All authors approved the final version for publication.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of the paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors appreciate the contribution of Mr. Dele Aiyepoku of the Department of Biochemistry, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria, for the technical assistance provided in the course of this study.

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